

Optimization of growth media of entomopathogenic fungus *Hirsutella citriformis*(speare)

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ABSTRACT

Attack of brown rice planthopper (*Nilaparvata lugens*) that cause hopperburn symptom is one of obstacles in rice cultivation. The entomopathogenic fungus *H. citriformis* could potentially control *N. lugens* in the field as epizootic of this fungus which is frequently observed among the brown planthopper (BPH) population. Unfortunately, the fungus growth in axenic media is slow. This study aims to determine optimum yeast extract (YE) concentration for growth of *H. citriformis* mycelia with the single spore method. The highest mycelia weight of 0716 was 7.90 when it was grew in Potato Dextrose containing 5 g /L YE in 14 days. While the weight of Bgr 0916 mycelia was 7.21 g when it was grew in Potato Dextrose containing 10 g / L YE in 14 days.

Keywords: *H. citriformis*, growth medium, mycelia, yeast extract.

INTRODUCTION

The rice plant (*Oryza sativa*) is a staple food source for most Indonesian society. One of the obstacles in rice cultivation is the attack of brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) (Hemiptera: Delphacidae) (Rombach et al., 1986). According to Baehaki and Jana (2015), BPH has high economic value because there are so many funds used for research, ranging from biology to control technology. In addition to the direct damage by sucking plant, Brown planthopper pests as well as spreaders of disease vector viruses that speed up the hupperburn rice plant. Entomopathogenic fungi *Hirsutella citriformis* (Speare) (Ascomycota: Ophiocordycipitaceae) (Simmons et al., 2015), almost always found attacking the BPH if the pest population explosions in the field (Chiu, 1979). Potential *H. citriformis* BPH to take control in the very high, airy evidenced frequently occurring epizootic in the BPH. This fungus is not much developed for BPH insect control. The problems and the potential of this being *H. citriformis* challenge in the laboratory to be developed into an effective control of the BPH agens.

Various forms of propagul entomopathogenic fungi can be used as active ingredients of bioinsecticide (Wahyudi, 2008). Studies on the utilization of *Hirsutella* sp. origin liquid media has not been much developed. Reproduction in scale fermentation must begin by performing optimization. The optimum fermentation of fungus medium is the medium that provides the nutrients include carbon, nitrogen, vitamins and minerals. Glucose is one of simple carbon source that is easily digested and used as an energy source for the growth of fungi (Nelson et al., 1996). The nitrogen source can come from such organic pepton, yeast extract and meat extract (Zambare, 2010). Research was conducted to obtain breeds of *Hirsutella* sp. optimization results that yield the best sporulation through the formation of synnemata. Optimization carried out included studies on the level of concentration and volume of yeast extract used.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fungus Inoculum Growth in Three Solid Media

Pure culture obtained from the mummy BPH infected with *H. citrifomis* in the field with incubation method and single spore technique (Toledo et al., 2013; Wawan et al., 2017). The pure culture of the fungus that has developed in the test tube is then propagated on solid media PDA + Y (yeast extract 5g/L and pH 6.8) in petri dishes. The source of the inoculum is then incubated at room temperature for 15 days. The maximum mycelia growth is then taken with cork temporary (D = 5 mm). Then it was grown on three types of media namely PDA, PDA + yeast extract (Criterion®) and PDA + yeast extract (Fermipan®). The concentration of each yeast is 5 g/ L. Tests on solid medium were carried out in petri dishes (diameter 8.5 cm), with a volume of 15 mL/cup and repeated 3 times. Incubation is carried out for 20 days at room temperature.

Optimization of the Fungal Growth on Liquid Media

Liquid medium are used for optimization is PD + yeast extract (Criterion®) (PDY) (Pérez-González et al., 2015). As treatment is the concentration of yeast extract in a medium that is 0, 2.5, 5, 10 and 15 g/L, and the volume of medium per container that is 12.5, 25 and 50 mL/container. Media containers used are glass bottles shaped like a box, placed lengthwise (Figure 1). Bottles have been sterilized in media content in an autoclave with 1210C temperature and pressure of 1 atmosphere for 90 minutes. Liquid media with pure breeds of mycelia pieces of fungal *Hirsutella* sp. is cold incubated originating from two isolates (Bgr 0716 and Bgr 0916).

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed by ANOVA in a completely randomized design (CRD) at a significant level of 5% using the SAS 9.1 program with the SAS Institute program (1990).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of Entomopathogenic Fungi *Hirsutella citriformis*

Two isolates of *Hirsutella sp.* those found to have almost the same characteristics. When hyphae growth is very slow on the media to be tilted PDAY (0.5% yeast extract). Germination of conidia to form hyphae mass until synemata formed in Bgr 0716 and Bgr 0916 isolates occurred between 38-92 days and 35-77 days, respectively. When the initial removal of hyphae mass in the test tube was carried out on some artificial media, the day the emergence of different synonyms was observed. The time of formation of synonyms ranging from hyphae mass on PDAY (C) and PDAY (F) media was formed 12-15 days later, whereas on PDA media formed after 4 days later (Table 1).

Table 1. Time of germination and formation of *Hirsutella sp.* on some artificial medium

Isolate	Media	Time of hyphae growth in the second quarter to synnemata (days)	
		Testube	Petridish
Bgr 0716	PDAY(C) (0.5%)	38-92	12-14 (6)
	PDAY(F) (0.5%)	-	12 (6)
	PDA	-	4 (6)
Bgr 0916	PDAY(C) (0.5%)	35-77	12-15 (6)
	PDAY(F) (0.5%)	-	14 (6)
	PDA	-	4 (6)

Description :PDAY (C) = *Potato dextrose agar yeast extract* (0.5%), PDAY (F) = *Potato dextrose agar yeast extract* (F) (0.5%). - = Not yet done.

Fungus Inoculum Growth in Three Solid Medium

The development of *H. citriformis* growth on PDA, PDAY (C) and PDAY (F) mycelia medium appears to clot and is very sticky on the media and container. Cultivation results of *H. citriformis* culture on PDAY media (C) obtained grayish white mycelia, growth zones form line folds, a form of growth that clots with almost the same diameter. In PDAY media (F) the growth of white mycelia, evenly distributed, is rather thin with the growth of new transparent mycelia. The growth of mycelia on irregular PDA media forms lumps and thick. In PDAY media (F) the growth of white, evenly distributed, thin mycelia with new mycelia growth appears transparent. The growth of

mycelia on irregular PDA media forms a lump and thick (Figure 1 A1-C1). The appearance of syndromes on PDA media is on the 4th day while in PDAY and PDAY (F) media between days 12-15 (Table 1). The pattern of formation of synnemata on PDA and PDAY (F) media appears in the middle part of *H. citriformis* culture pieces on PDAY synnemata media appears and forms on the edge of the media. The initial Synnemata appears white, gray and finally blackish in color (Figure 1 A2-B2).

Optimization of the Boletus Growth on Liquid Media

The use of liquid media in the mass production of *Hirsutella* sp. mycelia allows harvesting of mycelia can be done easily. Mycelia grow lumpy and spread to edge of container culture. Isolates Bgr 0716 has the highest average wet weight of mycelia on a volume of 50 mL of liquid medium, heavy mycelia gained 7.90 g IE. influence of wet weight of concentration YE against the highest at 15 g/L is 7.01 g. Whereas the lowest mycelia wet weights occurred on the volume of liquid media 12.5 mL of 0.22 g, concentrations of YE (Table 2). Development of propagul started on day 5 to 10th with the form of small bubbles, which then float white, the size of the breed began to widen and lumpy. From WAD then formed a collection of infective mycelia white the edge of the container. After 14 days the mycelia collection will meet the all parts of the container (Figure 1).

The rate of growth and development from the 2nd, 8th, 16th and 20th days showed almost the same increase. The highest growth rate of colonies isolated from Bgr 0716 and Bgr 0916 on PDAY (C) media was between 60.12-62.40 mm²/days. The development of mycelia diameter tends to be almost the same in 3 media with a range of 58.18-62.40 mm² / days. The average daily growth for 20 days is between 2.91-3.12 mm².

Figure 1. Forms of growth of mycelia and synnemata *H. citriformis*; (A1) PDA media, (A2) appear synnemata, (B1) PDAY (C) media, (B2) synnemata, (C1) PDAY (F) media, (C2) synnemata.

Table 2. The mycelia *H. citriformis* colony diameter growth rate in several solid media

Isolate	Media	(mm/days) ^a			
		Days to -			
		2	8	16	20
Bgr 0716	PDA	6.50±0.45a	27.00±1.41a	47.69±1.05a	62.10±0.78a
	PDAY (C)	6.88±0.07a	30.00±4.15a	47.08±2.05a	60.12±4.67a
	PDAY (F)	6.71±0.33a	28.03±0.88a	47.57±0.59a	59.62±1.88a
Bgr 0916	PDA	6.75±0.99a	27.13±1.51a	46.80±2.10a	61.27±1.92a
	PDAY (C)	6.30±0.61a	26.13±2.58a	50.71±1.20a	62.40±0.64a
	PDAY (F)	6.08±0.77a	24.78±2.71a	44.97±2.13a	58.18±1.18a

^aThe mean value followed by the same lowercase letters in each lane states that it is not significantly different from the Duncan test $\alpha=0.05$.

Fungus Growth Optimization in Liquid Media

The use of liquid media in mass production of *Hirsutella* sp. allowing harvesting of mycelia can be done easily. Mycelia grows clot and spreads to the edges of the culture container. Isolate Bgr 0716 had the highest mean mycelia wet weight on a liquid media volume of 50 mL, the weight of the mycelia obtained was 7.90 g. The effect of YE concentration on the highest wet weight at 15 g / L is 7.01 g. Whereas the lowest wet weight of mycelia occurred at 12.5 mL of liquid media volume of 0.22 g, YE concentration (Table 3). The development

of propagules begins on days 5 to 10 with the form of small dots, which then float white, the size of the culture begins to widen and clump. From the blob then form a white infective mycelia collection at the edge of the container. After 14 days the collection of mycelia will fill all parts of the container (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The growth of *H. citriformis* in liquid media in bottles contains yeast extract

Table 3. The wet weight of *H. citriformis* mycelia which was cultured in liquid media with different yeast extract concentrations.

Isolate	YE Concentration(g/L)	Mycelia wet weight (g)		
		12.5 mL	25 mL	50 mL
Isolate Bgr 0716	0	0.36±0.11c	0.42±0.06b	3.47±0.72c
	2.5	0.22±0.15c	1.21±0.43ab	7.41±1.32ab
	5	1.43±0.19ab	1.77±0.91a	7.90±0.52a
	10	1.08±0.81bc	2.13±0.79a	5.43±1.98bc
	15	2.08±0.69a	2.11±0.17a	7.01±0.12ab
Isolate Bgr 0916	0	0.29±0.01b	0.37±0.04b	3.14±0.27b
	2.5	0.54±0.07b	1.20±0.32ab	5.96±0.34a
	5	1.44±0.83ab	2.18±0.95a	6.87±1.03a
	10	1.21±0.17ab	2.23±1.16a	7.21±1.14a
	15	1.89±1.26a	2.02±0.15a	6.02±0.73a

^aThe mean value followed by the same lowercase letters in each lane states that it is not significantly different from the Duncan test $\alpha=0.05$.

Hirsutella citriformis entomopathogen fungal can be propagated on solid and liquid media containing yeast extract additives. The influence of YE concentration has been investigated by Hall *et al.* (2012). Growth in culture media is very slow (Subandiyah *et al.*, 2000; Meyer *et al.*, 2007; Casique-Valdes *et al.*, 2011; Pérez-Gonzalez *et al.*, 2015). Medium PDA with the addition of YE becomes richer in nutritional content and is beneficial for the growth of the *Hirsutella* genus (Dwiastuti and Yunimar, 2016).

The results of the production of wet mycelia isolates Bgr 0716 and Bgr 0916 on a medium volume of 50 mL get the highest wet weight, the larger the volume of liquid media in the container can stimulate the formation of more blastospores and propagules. Increased mycelia growth must be balanced with the amount of media volume and YE concentration that is balanced. The addition of YE concentration and volume of liquid media affect the results of wet mycelia production.

CONCLUSIONS

Entomopathogenic fungus *H. citriformis* has the best sporulation ability on media containing yeast extract (C) with a concentration of 5 g / L. mycelia *H. citriformis* can then be a potential source of inoculum to BPH pests control.

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